

Patent Ductus Arteriosus: The Aortopulmonary Shunt!

Deeksha Acharya, M.D.^a, Abdul Moiz Qureshi, M.D.^a, Taylor Goulding-Avedisian, M.D.^a,
Bassam Omar, M.D., Ph.D.^{a,b}, Christopher Malozzi, D.O.^a, Suganya Manoharan, M.D.^a

Description

The above transthoracic echocardiogram (TTE) images with color flow Doppler demonstrate flow through a patent ductus arteriosus (PDA). In the short axis view across the right ventricular outflow tract, figure A shows the flow in the PDA during diastole, coinciding with pulmonic insufficiency jet, while figure B reveals persistent PDA flow in systole.

In the suprasternal notch views across the aortic arch, figure C demonstrates subtle PDA flow at the level of the distal arch. Figure D, obtained from a different patient, demonstrates the distal tip of a PDA occlusion device placed for a hemodynamically significant PDA, with no residual shunting on subsequent color flow Doppler.

Discussion

PDA is uncommon and while it is reported in about 1/2000 term infants (~ 5-10% of congenital heart disease cases), it appears to be more common in preterm infants, up to 20 – 60% [1]. It is often an incidental finding in the adult with a prevalence of 5/10,000.

The ductus arteriosus closes after birth leaving the fibrous *ligamentum arteriosum*. Many intrinsic and extrinsic factors contribute to ductus closure including structural, hemodynamic, and molecular aspects of the ductus, in addition to maternal infectious and/ or environmental factors [2]. Genetic factors may also play an important role.

A PDA results in a continuous murmur on physical examination, the intensity of which depends on the size of the shunt [3]. Low diastolic blood pressure and a wide pulse pressure have also been reported. Diagnosis and hemodynamic significance are usually confirmed by echocardiography.

While pharmacologic agents may be an option to promote PDA closure in infancy, the indications and approaches to PDA closure in adults are less clear. Surgical and percutaneous techniques have been reported with success [4]. Severe pulmonary hypertension in general contraindicates PDA closure. However, trial balloon occlusion, if hemodynamically tolerated, may indicate reversibility of the severe pulmonary hypertension and allow for safe permanent percutaneous PDA closure in such cases [5].

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a Division of Cardiology. University of South Alabama, Mobile, AL 36617

b Corresponding Author: Bassam Omar, Division of Cardiology, University of South Alabama, 2451 USA Medical Center Dr., Mobile, AL 36617, USA.

Email: bomar@health.southalabama.edu

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